

UNDERSTANDING SPS STUDENTS MOTIVATIONAL FACTOR IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION SUBJECT AND ITS EFFECT ON ACADEMIC ENGAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This quantitative study aimed to understand the motivational factors of SPS students in Physical Education subject and its effect on academic engagement in one of the public secondary schools in Sariaya, Quezon for the academic year 2024–2025. Specifically, the study understands the level of motivational factors in terms of participation in the PE subject, interaction with peers and instructors, and completion of academic and sports-related requirements. For the perceived effects, this study focused on self-determination, effort and persistence, and study strategies. Researchers employed a descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing a self-made and validated questionnaire. The study involved 30 Grade 10 SPS students as respondents, and the data were analyzed using Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) and Spearman rho correlation. Findings showed that the level of motivational factors was rated “High” across all dimensions, with the following WAM scores: participation in PE subject (3.64), interaction with peers and instructors (3.65), and completion of academic and sports-related requirements (3.62). Similarly, for the perceived effect of motivational factors on academic engagement, the results were also interpreted as “High,” with self-determination (3.66), effort and persistence (3.67), and study strategies (3.62) emerging as key contributors. The Spearman rho correlation result of 0.846 with a p-value of 0.000 confirmed a statistically significant and strong positive relationship between motivational factors and academic engagement. Based on

the results, a motivational intervention video is crafted targeted strategies in PE classes to support students holistic academic and athletic development.

Keywords: *motivational factors, academic engagement, SPS students, Physical Education.*

INTRODUCTION

The motivation of students in Physical Education (PE) classes is a critical factor that affects academic engagement and overall performance. For students enrolled in Special Programs for Sports (SPS), understanding what drives motivation is essential for enhancing their involvement and academic success. Despite the importance of motivation, there is limited knowledge, specifically, understanding the factors affecting academic outcomes. The SPS is an initiative by the Department of Education aimed at developing the athletic talents of students while ensuring their academic growth. According to the Department of Education (2015), the program seeks to address the needs of students who exhibit potential in various sports disciplines by providing specialized training alongside the standard curriculum.

Motivation plays a central role in how students approach learning tasks and persist in achieving academic goals. It encompasses both internal and external factors that stimulate individuals to initiate, direct, and sustain behavior. These motivational influences may be intrinsic, such as personal interest, or extrinsic, like rewards or recognition (Schunk, Pintrich, & Meece, 2015). For students, the right balance of these motivators can drive enthusiasm, improve resilience, and enhance academic performance.

Closely related to motivation is academic engagement, a multidimensional construct that reflects how much effort students invest behaviorally, emotionally, and cognitively in their learning processes. In practical terms, this includes active participation in class activities, emotional commitment to learning, and strategic thinking when completing academic tasks (Martin, 2020). Research highlights that positive motivational factors such as goal-setting, teacher support, and a sense of competence boost engagement (Ryan & Deci, 2020). In contrast, negative influences like pressure, fear of failure, or lack of autonomy can diminish motivation and increase academic stress (Skinner et al., 2008).

Despite strong theoretical foundations, current national and international education reports suggest that motivation in PE is often undervalued. For instance, a 2022 UNESCO assessment reported that 40% of students globally lose interest in physical activities due to academic stress and insufficient support. Similarly, a 2021 study by the Philippine Department of Education (DepEd) noted that SPS students often struggle to manage their academic and athletic workloads, leading to declining interest in PE classes.

These findings emphasize the urgency to explore the factors affecting motivation in PE, particularly how they impact engagement among SPS students. Understanding these factors is essential for educators and policymakers to design effective programs that enhance student motivation and promote a healthy balance between academics and athletics. This objective aligns with several educational policies, including the Student-Athletes Protection Act (Republic Act No. 10676), DepEd Order No. 88, s. 2010, and DepEd Memorandum No. 60, s. 2019, all of which advocate for holistic support for student-athletes and recognize the role of PE in overall student well-being.

This study aimed to address these gaps by examining the motivational factors effect on SPS student's academic engagement in PE. Specifically, to understand how factors like self-determination, effort and persistence, and study strategies affect students participation in PE activities, their interaction with peers and instructors, and their completion of academic and sports-related requirements. The research is important as it contributes to the field of education by shedding light on how to better support SPS students in balancing academics and sports. It also provides insights that can guide educators, policymakers, and school administrators in creating more effective programs that foster motivation, engagement, and success in both academics and athletics.

Research Questions

This study aimed to understand the SPS students' motivational factor in Physical Education subject and its effect on academic engagement. Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What is the level of motivational factors in PE subject of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Participation in PE activities;
 - 1.2 Interaction with Peers and Instructors; and
 - 1.3 Completion of Academic and Sports Related Requirement?
2. What is the perceived effect of motivational factor to the academic engagement of the respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1 Self-Determination;
 - 2.2 Effort and Persistence; and
 - 2.3 Study Strategies?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the motivational factors and academic engagement of the respondents?
4. Based on the research findings, what motivational intervention video can be created by researchers to purpose?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive correlational research design within a quantitative approach to understand the motivational factors of SPS students in Physical Education (PE) subjects and their effect on academic engagement.

According to Creswell and Creswell (2018), descriptive correlational research is a non-experimental method that describes relationships between two or more variables without manipulating them. The researchers observed and measured variables as they naturally occurred, using statistical analyses to identify patterns of association. The quantitative approach allowed for the systematic investigation of numerical data to quantify variables, assess relationships, and draw objective conclusions. It relied on structured tools, such as a researcher-made questionnaire and statistical analysis, to test hypotheses and support findings with measurable evidence.

This research design was appropriate for the study as it allowed the researchers to examine the relationship between motivational factors and academic engagement among SPS students in PE without altering any conditions. Since the goal was to determine whether a significant correlation existed between motivation and academic engagement, the descriptive correlational method provided a solid framework for gathering and analyzing relevant data. Furthermore, the design enabled the exploration of multiple variables simultaneously using statistical tools such as Weighted Average Mean (WAM) and Spearman rho, making it an efficient and effective approach for identifying trends and associations. These findings were intended to inform future educational strategies and motivational interventions to enhance student performance and participation in PE classes.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in one secondary public institution in Sariaya, Quezon, a specialized institution that offered the Special Program in Sports (SPS). The school was known for its strong emphasis on physical education and athletic development, providing students with structured training and academic support. The SPS program catered to students who were actively engaged in various sports, balancing both their academic and athletic commitments. Given its dual focus on academics and physical training, the school served as an ideal setting to examine the motivational factors influencing students' performance in PE and their academic engagement.

The rationale for selecting this school as the research locale stemmed from its well-established SPS program and the observed academic challenges faced by student-athletes. This study aimed to understand these issues and provide insights that could help educators, coaches, and administrators develop strategies to enhance both athletic and academic motivation. By focusing on this particular institution, the research ensured

that the findings were relevant and applicable to similar educational settings with specialized sports programs.

Research Population and Sample

The study specifically focused on students enrolled in SPS program during the academic year 2024–2025. This group was selected due to their active participation in both academic and athletic activities, making them suitable respondents for the study's focus on motivational factors and academic engagement.

The researchers employed a purposive sampling technique, which is a non-probability sampling method used to select participants based on specific characteristics essential to the research. In this case, students were selected based on their active involvement in the SPS program and enrolled as grade 10 students in the chosen locale. According to Etikan, Musa, and Alkassim (2016), purposive sampling is ideal when researchers need to gather in-depth information from a targeted group who are most likely to provide relevant insights on the research topic.

A total of thirty (30) Grade 10 SPS students were selected as respondents. The use of purposive sampling combined with this formula allowed for a focused and meaningful analysis of how motivational factors relate to academic engagement in the PE setting.

Research Instrument

The researchers used a self-made questionnaire to understand the motivational factors of SPS students in the Physical Education (PE) subject and their effect on academic engagement.

The questionnaire consisted of two parts. Part one focused on the level of motivational factors in terms of participation in PE activities, interaction with peers and instructors, and completion of academic and sports-related requirement. While part two focused on the perceived effect of motivational factors to the academic engagement of the respondents with the following variables: self-determination, effort and persistence, study strategies. There are ten statements for each variable, with a total of 60 statements. For the easy understanding, the researchers used a checklist questionnaire using a four point Likert Scale. The respondents were guided by the rating scale value of "4" high, "3" moderate high, "2" moderate low and "1" low.

The instrument was initially reviewed by the research adviser for clarity and relevance, then revised based on feedback. To ensure validity, the final version was evaluated and validated by two Physical Education specialists who confirmed the alignment of the instrument with the goal of the study. And also, an English critique that checks the grammar of the questionnaire.

Data Gathering Procedures

Before the actual data collection, the researchers formally sought approval from the school principal of the chosen locale. A letter of request was submitted, explaining the purpose, objectives, and significance of the study, including the intent to understand SPS students' motivational factors in Physical Education and its effect on academic engagement. The letter also identified the SPS students as the main respondents. Upon approval, the researchers coordinated with school representatives to arrange a suitable schedule and venue for the data gathering process.

When the permission was granted, the researchers administered the self-made checklist-type questionnaire designed to understand motivational factors in PE and their relationship to academic engagement. The validated questionnaires were then administered by the researchers to the target respondents. Before distribution, the purpose of the study and instructions for answering the questionnaire were clearly explained to ensure understanding. Adequate time was allotted for the respondents to complete the questionnaire honestly and thoughtfully. After collecting, the researchers carefully organized, tallied, and encoded the responses for analysis. Appropriate quantitative techniques were then applied to interpret the data and draw meaningful conclusions.

Statistical Treatment

The researchers used the following statistical treatment to analyze the data gathered precisely.

Regarding the level of motivational factors in PE subject and its perceived effect on the academic engagement of the respondents, the researchers used a Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) as a statistical treatment. The formula is as follows:

$$W = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i X_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i}$$

Where:

W = Weighted Average

n = Numbers of Terms to be Average

w_i = Corresponding Weight

X_i = Value of any particular

The researchers used a 4 - Point Likert scale and interpreted the result for SOP 1 and SOP 2 using the continuous scale below;

Point Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.25 - 4.00	High
3	2.50 - 3.24	Moderate High
2	1.75 - 2.49	Moderate Low

1	1.00 - 1.74	Low
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Additionally, for the analysis of the significant relationship between the motivational factors and academic engagement of the respondents the researchers used Spearman Rho as statistical treatment. The formula shown below:

$$p = 1 - \frac{6\sum d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

Where:

p = Weighted Mean

n = Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient

di = difference between to ranks of each observation

n = number of observation

RESULTS

Part I. Level of Motivational Factors in PE subjects

Table 1

Level of Motivational Factors in PE subject in terms of Participation in PE activities

No.	Statements	WAM	VI
8	I am motivated to participate in PE when I see improvements in my abilities.	3.83	High
6	I enjoy participating in PE activities regardless of my skill level.	3.80	High
2	I follow the instructions given by my PE instructors.	3.67	High
3	I exert effort to improve my physical performance.	3.67	High
5	I push myself harder in PE when there is a competition involved.	3.67	High
10	I attend my PE classes regularly.	3.67	High
4	I continue to engage in PE activities even when challenges arise.	3.60	High
1	I actively participate in warm-ups and skill-building drills.	3.57	High
7	I stay committed to PE activities even when I feel tired.	3.57	High
9	I am more likely to participate in PE when my classmates or teammates encourage me.	3.33	High
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.64	High

Table 2

Level of Motivational Factors in PE subject in terms of Interaction with Peers and Instructors

No.	Statements	WAM	VI
4	I collaborate with my teammates during group activities to achieve a common goal.	3.80	High
9	I appreciate it when my instructor provides constructive criticism to help me improve.	3.80	High

6	I actively listen to my instructor's feedback to improve my performance.	3.77	High
8	I follow the instructions given by my instructor to ensure I'm performing activities correctly.	3.73	High
10	I feel supported by my instructor when I encounter difficulties in PE class.	3.67	High
5	I learn new techniques or strategies from my peers during practice sessions.	3.63	High
2	I encourage my peers when they are struggling with physical activity or skill.	3.60	High
7	I feel comfortable asking my instructor for help when I do not understand an exercise or concept.	3.60	High
1	I often work together with my classmates to practice PE skills.	3.57	High
3	I feel motivated to perform well when my classmates cheer me on.	3.37	High
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.65	High

Table 3
Level of Motivational Factors in PE subject in terms of Completion of Academic and Sports-Related Requirements

No.	Statements	WAM	VI
9	I ensure active participation in required PE activities and sports programs.	3.77	High
10	I aim to achieve high scores in PE assessments to maintain my academic standing.	3.77	High
5	I am increasing my training efforts in preparation for sports competitions.	3.70	High
8	I track my progress in PE and set goals for improvement.	3.67	High
4	I prioritize completing all PE practical tasks to meet instructor expectations.	3.60	High
6	I take responsibility for improving my skills in PE.	3.60	High
7	I put effort into both the practical and theoretical aspects of PE.	3.60	High
3	I am adequately preparing for PE tests and skill evaluations.	3.57	High
2	I participate in practical and theoretical PE activities to fulfill academic requirements.	3.53	High
1	I complete and submit PE-related written assignments on time.	3.43	High
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.62	High

Part II. Perceived Effect of Motivational Factor to Academic Engagement

Table 4

Perceived Effect of Motivational Factor to the Academic Engagement in terms of Self-Determination

No.	Statement	WAM	VI
4	I become more disciplined in practicing and refining my skills.	3.73	High
2	I take ownership of my learning, which helps me stay committed to my goals.	3.70	High
5	I maintain a strong work ethic, knowing that my progress depends on my effort.	3.70	High
7	I learn to manage setbacks effectively and continue striving for improvement.	3.70	High
10	I feel a deep sense of achievement when I reach my self-set goals.	3.70	High
6	I feel more in control of my success, leading to greater personal satisfaction.	3.63	High
8	I stay engaged in PE activities because I see personal growth as a reward.	3.63	High
1	I stay motivated to improve in PE without relying on external rewards.	3.60	High
3	I develop confidence to face challenges and push my physical limits.	3.60	High
9	I develop a sense of independence in training and decision-making.	3.60	High
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.66	High

Table 5

Perceived Effect of Motivational Factor to the Academic Engagement in terms of Effort and Persistence

No.	Statement	WAM	VI
5	I pay attention to my instructor's feedback and apply it to improve.	3.77	High
3	I challenge myself to perform better in every P.E. session	3.73	High
1	I always give my best effort during P.E. activities, regardless of difficulty.	3.70	High
2	I actively work on improving my physical skills in P.E. class.	3.70	High
6	I continue participating in P.E. even when I find activities challenging.	3.70	High
8	I stay motivated to complete physical activities, even when I feel tired.	3.70	High
10	I push through difficulties in P.E. because I believe improvement takes time.	3.70	High
9	I try multiple times until I successfully perform a skill or routine.	3.67	High
4	I take the initiative to practice outside of class to enhance my performance.	3.53	High

7	I do not easily give up when I struggle with a new skill or exercise.	3.53	High
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.67	High

Table 6

Perceived Effect of Motivational Factor to the Academic Engagement in terms of Study Strategies

No.	Statement	WAM	VI
7	I analyze my past performances to identify strengths and areas for improvement.	3.77	High
9	I take short breaks between study sessions to maintain focus and avoid burnout.	3.73	High
4	I summarize key points in my own words to enhance understanding.	3.67	High
2	I break complex topics into smaller, manageable sections.	3.60	High
3	I use active recall techniques, such as self-quizzing, to reinforce learning.	3.60	High
8	I develop a positive mindset by staying motivated even after making mistakes.	3.60	High
10	I minimize distractions by creating a focused study environment.	3.60	High
1	I create a study plan and stick to its schedule consistently.	3.57	High
5	I set specific goals for each study session to track my progress.	3.57	High
6	I watch instructional videos or demonstrations to improve my techniques.	3.50	High
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.62	High

Part III. Relationship between the Motivational Factors and Academic Engagement

Table 7

Relationship between the Motivational Factors and Academic Engagement

Significance Level	Degrees of Freedom	Test Statistic	p value	Critical Value	Statistical Decision	Interpretation
1%	28	.846	.000	0.475	Reject H_0	Significant

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the level of motivational factors in PE subjects in terms of participation in PE activities. The overall average WAM is 3.64, which falls under the "High" interpretation category. This implies that students generally demonstrate a strong level of motivation when it comes to taking part in PE classes. The consistency in high

scores across different indicators reflects a positive perception toward physical education, suggesting that students are engaged and willing to participate actively.

The highest WAM, recorded at 3.83, corresponds to the statement “I am motivated to participate in PE when I see improvements in my abilities.” This indicates that students are highly driven by self-improvement and visible personal progress. They are more inclined to stay involved in PE when they recognize that their efforts result in measurable development.

On the other hand, the lowest WAM is 3.33, which pertains to the statement “I am more likely to participate in PE when my classmates or teammates encourage me.” Although this still falls within the "High" range, it is relatively lower compared to the other motivational indicators. This suggests that while social encouragement from peers is appreciated, it is not the most influential factor in driving student participation. Students tend to prioritize personal achievement over social influence when it comes to engaging in PE activities.

These findings are further supported by Uddin et al. (2020), who noted that frequent participation in PE correlates with improved physical activity levels and engagement. The current data reflects that students are likely to stay involved in PE activities when they feel a sense of personal progress and accomplishment, which may, in turn, promote better academic focus and cognitive performance as described in the broader literature.

In addition, the literature by Donnelly et al. (2016) underscores that regular engagement in structured physical activities, such as those in PE programs, has positive effects on academic outcomes. The high participation motivation observed in this study suggests a favorable context for leveraging PE as a means to improve overall student academic engagement and performance. This is particularly relevant in programs like SPS, where physical development is closely tied to the broader educational experience.

Table 2 on the next page presents the level of motivational factors in PE based on students' interaction with their peers and instructors. The average Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) was calculated at 3.65, falling under the "High" interpretation range. This suggests that students view interactions with peers and instructors as significant contributors to their motivation in PE settings. A generally high average WAM across all indicators implies that a socially supportive classroom climate fosters better student engagement.

The highest WAM recorded, 3.80, was shared by two indicators: “I collaborate with my teammates during group activities to achieve a common goal” and “I appreciate it when my instructor provides constructive criticism to help me improve.” This indicates that team collaboration and teacher feedback are highly valued motivational elements.

Conversely, the lowest WAM in the table is 3.37, for the item “I feel motivated to perform well when my classmates cheer me on.” While still categorized as “High,” this

score is comparatively lower than other indicators.

Table 3 presents the responses regarding their motivation to complete academic and sports-related requirements in PE. The indicators with the highest WAM (3.77) were “I ensure active participation in required PE activities and sports programs” and “I aim to achieve high scores in PE assessments to maintain my academic standing,” showing that students are driven by both personal commitment and academic performance. This highlights that motivation in PE is not limited to physical involvement but also includes a desire to succeed academically.

Regarding the completion of academic and sports-related requirements, the statements “I ensure active participation in required PE activities and sports programs” and “I aim to achieve high scores in PE assessments to maintain my academic standing” both obtained the highest mean score (WAM = 3.77), highlighting the importance students place on fulfilling obligations and academic success. The lowest mean score was for “I complete and submit PE-related written assignments on time” (WAM = 3.43), suggesting that written tasks may be perceived as less engaging or prioritized compared to practical performance-based requirements.

For instance, Fuchs et al. (2021) found that student-athletes who manage their time effectively and receive institutional support are better equipped to balance their athletic and academic responsibilities. This finding implies that creating supportive environments, especially for written and administrative tasks, is crucial for sustaining holistic student performance.

Additionally, Hasnain (2023) reported that sports participation reduces academic burnout and promotes student well-being, making it an effective motivator in helping students persist through challenging academic obligations. Lamb et al. (2021) and Hein (2015) also reinforce the idea that when students experience a nurturing and autonomy-supportive classroom environment, they are more likely to persevere in completing both physical and academic requirements.

Table 4 on the next page presents the perceived effects of motivational factors on academic engagement among SPS students, focusing specifically on self-determination. The overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) was recorded at 3.65, falling under the “High” category. This indicates that students generally exhibit a strong level of self-determined behavior in the context of PE. The responses suggest that students are motivated by internal factors such as personal goals, self-discipline, and a desire to improve traits commonly associated with effective academic and physical performance. The highest WAM, 3.73, was rated for the statement, “I become more disciplined in practicing and refining my skills.” This highlights that discipline and consistent practice are central elements of self-determination among students. The data suggests that students value the process of self-improvement and are willing to commit time and effort to refining their physical abilities, even without immediate external incentives.

On the other hand, the lowest WAM, 3.60, was shared in three items: “I stay motivated to improve in PE without relying on external rewards,” “I develop confidence to face challenges and push my physical limits,” and “I develop a sense of independence in training and decision-making.” While these still fall within the “High” range, they reflect areas where students may need more structured encouragement and support to fully internalize these self-determined traits.

These nuances are supported by González-Cutre et al. (2015), who found that PE environments promoting autonomy, competence, and relatedness foster higher self-determined motivation and long-term engagement in health-promoting behaviors. Similarly, López-García et al. (2023) found that pre-service PE teachers who experienced satisfaction in autonomy and competence were more likely to engage in academic activities out of intrinsic motivation, which is critical for long-term educational success.

Table 5 on the succeeding page shows the perceived effect of motivational factors on academic engagement, specifically in terms of effort and persistence among students in the Special Program in Sports (SPS). The overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) of 3.67 falls within the High category, indicating that students generally perceive themselves as highly motivated and persistent during P.E. activities.

The highest WAM, 3.77, was observed in the item “I pay attention to my instructor's feedback and apply it to improve,” which suggests that students greatly value and use feedback to guide their progress. This demonstrates a strong reflective practice and responsiveness to instructional input, key components of effective learning and performance. In contrast, the lowest WAMs, both at 3.53, were recorded for the statements “I take the initiative to practice outside of class to enhance my performance” and “I do not easily give up when I struggle with a new skill or exercise.” Although these are still considered high, the slightly lower scores may point to opportunities for encouraging more independent practice and resilience beyond the classroom setting.

These observations echo Donnelly et al. (2017), who suggest that structured physical education can instill valuable coping mechanisms and mental endurance. Similarly, Ashraf et al. (2023) emphasize that a growth mindset, cultivated through physical activity, enhances a student’s ability to rebound from failure, an essential trait for academic persistence.

Table 6, as seen on the previous page, presents the perceived effectiveness of various study strategies used by students in the Special Program in Sports (SPS). The overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) was 3.62, which falls under the “High” category. This indicates that SPS students generally consider their study strategies to be effective in supporting their academic engagement and learning in Physical Education. The results suggest that students are using a combination of cognitive, metacognitive, and self-regulation techniques to enhance both their understanding and performance. According to Schunk, Pintrich, and Meece (2015), students who apply reflective and organized study strategies tend to demonstrate greater academic persistence and success, especially in practical and performance-based subjects like PE.

The highest WAM, 3.77, was recorded for the item “I analyze my past performances to identify strengths and areas for improvement.” This reflects a strong student preference for reflective learning, where reviewing past actions serves as a foundation for continuous improvement. These results indicate that SPS students are not only practicing effective cognitive and metacognitive strategies but also showing an awareness of mental well-being and study-life balance. These strategies correspond with the empirically supported techniques reviewed by Dunlosky et al. (2013), who emphasized that approaches such as summarization, spaced learning, and chunking information into manageable parts significantly enhance retention and comprehension when properly implemented.

Meanwhile, 3.50, the lowest WAM, was tallied for the statement, “I watch instructional videos or demonstrations to improve my techniques.” Although it still falls within the “High” range, it is noticeably lower than the other strategies. This trend may be influenced by cultural or contextual learning preferences, as described by Richardson and Bond (2017). Their cross-cultural study revealed significant variations in the use of cognitive strategies, with some students favoring direct interaction or experiential methods over mediated resources like videos. Such preferences further underscore the importance of tailoring instructional techniques to students’ cultural and contextual learning styles.

Table 7 presents the results of the statistical analysis conducted to determine whether a significant relationship exists between motivational factors and academic engagement among SPS students. The data reveal that the test statistic was 0.846, with a critical value of 0.475 at the 1% significance level and 28 degrees of freedom. Since the test statistic exceeds the critical value, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, indicating a statistically significant relationship between the two variables.

This result suggests that motivational factors have a strong and meaningful influence on students’ academic engagement in the context of Physical Education. The very low p-value of .000 further confirms the reliability of this finding, emphasizing that the likelihood of this result occurring by chance is extremely small. This implies that as students’ motivation increases, whether through personal discipline, peer support, or reflective learning, their engagement in academic activities also improves. These findings align with previous research by Schunk, Pintrich, and Meece (2015), who noted that motivation plays a critical role in shaping students’ level of effort, persistence, and overall academic involvement.

Conclusions

The findings have led the researchers to the following conclusions. After analyzing the data, the current researchers arrived at the following insights.

1. Most of the respondents consider interaction with peers and instructors as the highest level of motivational factors in PE subject.
2. For the perceived effects of motivational factors on the academic engagement of the respondents, effort and persistence are considered as the most effective.

3. There is a significant relationship between the motivational factors and academic engagement of the respondents.
4. A motivational intervention video was created by the researchers entitled "Igniting Passion: The Power of Motivation in Physical Education" to inspire SPS students to enhance their participation and academic performance in PE classes.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. The SPS students are encouraged to reflect on what drives their interest in Physical Education, whether it's personal goals, enjoyment of the subject, peer support, or the desire to excel in sports. Understanding their motivation can help sustain their commitment and improve their academic engagement.
2. Teachers and Coaches may incorporate motivational strategies such as goal setting, student choice, and positive reinforcement within PE classes. Recognizing and addressing individual interests (e.g., team sports, fitness challenges, or dance) can increase intrinsic motivation and academic engagement.
3. School Administrators may also encourage professional development for PE teachers to adopt motivational teaching strategies aligned with students' needs. By fostering a supportive and engaging PE environment, administrators can help improve not only physical fitness but also academic engagement and overall student well-being.
4. Researchers are encouraged to further explore the underlying reasons behind the motivational factors identified in this study by incorporating qualitative methods, such as interviews or focus group discussions, to support and enrich the quantitative findings. This would provide a more comprehensive understanding of why certain factors influence academic engagement in Physical Education.
5. Future Researchers are encouraged to expand the scope of the study by including a larger and more diverse population beyond SPS students to enhance generalizability. They may also explore additional variables such as teaching strategies, environmental factors, or socio-emotional influences that may affect both motivation and academic engagement in Physical Education.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers strictly adhered to ethical standards throughout the study. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents. The respondents were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. No names or identifying information were required in the questionnaire. Moreover, the data collected was used solely for academic purposes and securely stored to protect

participant privacy. Respect for the dignity, rights, and well-being of the respondents was upheld at all times during the data gathering process.

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